

**SOCIAL MOBILIZATION AND ONLINE ENGAGEMENT: TAPPING SOCIAL
CAPITAL TO IMPROVE THE SCHOOL'S FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT
SYSTEM IN CRISIS RESPONSE AND RECOVERY**

An Action Research Submitted to the Schools

Division Research Committee

Division of Bohol

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SOCIAL MOBILIZATION AND ONLINE ENGAGEMENT: TAPPING SOCIAL CAPITAL TO IMPROVE THE SCHOOL'S FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN CRISIS RESPONSE AND RECOVERY

ABSTRACT

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The skillful management of financial resources to fulfill school obligations and needs is very crucial, especially in times of crisis situations. The ability of schools to mobilize needed resources speeds up recovery after a crisis and greatly impacts the delivery of quality education. Thus, it is imperative that schools must be able to come up with proactive strategies to raise funds from stakeholders in order to fill in the fiscal gaps and resolve their needs timely. The main objective of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of social mobilization and online engagement as a strategy to improve the school's financial management system in relation to crisis response and recovery. This study explored data by reviewing school Brigada Eskwela documents and data from a survey questionnaire given to teachers and parents to attain the intended purpose of the study. The study found that social mobilization and online engagement were effective ways of tapping into the school's social capital. Moreover, they were found to be very effective strategies in improving the school's crisis response and speeding up its recovery. In addition, the amount raised by the school was significantly higher than in the previous years. The strategies were found to be effective based on the perception of the teachers and parents. Finally, this study recommends that school heads as prime financial managers of schools should demonstrate competence, leadership, and trustworthiness in financial management to ensure the sustainability of quality education provision in schools.

Keywords: financial management, social mobilization, online engagement, social capital, exploratory sequential mixed-method, action research, Bohol, Philippines

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Context and Rationale

The financial position of schools greatly impacts how they respond to their needs, especially in terms of recovery after crisis situations like typhoons and earthquakes. Without the needed financial resources to address their recovery needs, schools will be handicapped in delivering timely and appropriate responses. The skillful management of financial resources contributes greatly to the success of any school plan, which in turn, improves overall school performance (Bilkisu, 2018).

With the onslaught of the COVID-19 pandemic that affected the world, the problems of school heads mainly revolved around two concerns: the resources of the school and students, and the decisions made, regarding educational and instructional processes (Ceyhun, 2021). With this in mind, school resilience and recovery can be enhanced by internal and external stakeholders to cope with extreme events by playing essential roles, either by reinforcing government-led efforts or by filling the institutional gaps and voids left by the government. By donating money, equipment, and other needed supplies, civil society actors contribute to social resilience and recovery (Cai, 2021).

On December 16, 2021, super typhoon Rai, (locally named Odette) struck a large part of the Visayan Islands, in particular the eastern part of Bohol and nearby islands. The super typhoon destroyed homes, schools, and other critical infrastructures. In its July 25, 2022 issue, the Bohol Chronicle published its report that only 32 schools out of 398 were allocated repair funds, leaving the 366 schools in dire situations as to the repair of their

damaged classrooms and buildings. (Dejaresco, 2022). This was excluding the needed replacement of their damaged equipment and tools.

One of these schools was Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts, located in Puerto San Pedro, Bien Unido, Bohol. The school was badly damaged after the super typhoon and it was clear that the road to recovery was dire without the financial resources needed.

As provided by DepEd Order 40 series of 2015, this is the time when the school can use its social capital so that capacities can be mobilized during recovery. The aforementioned order stipulates the importance of building partnerships with both internal and external educational stakeholders to respond to the needs of the school in terms of the resources and capacity to enhance the delivery of quality basic education.

The school budget which comes from its MOOE (Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses) allocation was clearly not enough to cover the huge money needed to repair the damaged buildings and to procure the needed educational equipment and tools to replace those damaged by the typhoon. In this light, the researcher understood the importance of leveling up the school's social mobilization and online engagement efforts to raise funds for the school to timely respond to the recovery needs after the devastation brought by typhoon Odette.

The importance of tapping internal and external stakeholders was very clear to help bridge the fiscal gaps of the school. There was a need to find alternative sources for additional school funds since clearly, the school MOOE was not enough to cover all the school's financial needs. To ensure a safe and secure learning environment for the learners as they go back to school, immediate action was imperative.

It was at this point that the researcher understood the importance of building social connections and online engagement as a way for the school to reach out to potential benefactors. In this digital era, implementing digital transformations in the way we do things, greatly contributes to improving the quality of life in general and education in particular (Dung, 2021).

It was crucial to build partnerships with stakeholders to enable speedy school recovery in time for the return of the face-to-face classes of the learners. As such, the school embarked on massive traditional and social media initiatives to influence awareness and raise community engagement in support of its recovery plans and programs (Albana, 2022).

It is crucial to note that before the COVID-19 pandemic and typhoon Odette, the school already started to put in place initiatives that build its social capital both traditionally and by using digital means. The school leadership understood the importance of building and practicing diverse forms of social capital before a disturbance so that capacities can be mobilized immediately during recovery (Ozanne, 2021).

Research Questions

The researcher designed this study to determine the effectiveness of the social mobilization and online engagement strategy of Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts, Bien Unido District for the school year 2021-2022 in terms of tapping its social capital to improve its financial management system in crisis and recovery response.

Specifically, the answers to the following questions were sought:

1. Was there an improvement in the school's financial resources generated after the strategy was implemented?
2. What is the level of understanding of the participants as to the importance of the implemented strategy in improving the school's financial management system in terms of crisis response and speed of recovery after the strategy was implemented?
3. Was the strategy effective according to the perception of the teachers and parents?
4. How can the strategy be further improved?

Strategy

To solve the financial gaps of the school in terms of its recovery needs, the researcher thought of a strategy to bridge the gaps. Thus, social mobilization and social engagement strategies were conceptualized to improve the school's financial management responses after the crisis brought on by super typhoon Odette and aggravated by the still ongoing COVID-19 pandemic.

Pre-Implementation

In the months prior, the researcher took a strategic move by assessing the potential value of its social capital. Upon realizing its huge potential based on the initial assessment, the researcher proceeded to tap the three forms of social capital embedded in the school system for the last five years. These initiatives focused on tapping into structural (connections among civil society actors), cognitive (shared goals and values among actors),

and relational (trust between actors) dimensions. The researcher also expanded latent capacities for self-organizing and learning in the school through DRRM (Disaster Risk Reduction & Management) and basic Financial Literacy capacity-building training for the teachers and teacher-leaders.

Figure 1. Implementation Plan Diagram

Implementation

The researcher made several preparations in tapping into the social capital of the school. A coordination meeting was first held to orient all teachers on how to go about the social mobilization and social engagement strategies. Then, the school finance team was briefed as to their roles and responsibilities. Committees were made to boost social mobilization and online engagement strategies.

In addition, another crucial move taken was to look into the teachers' social capital and identify possible partners and donors that can be tapped to help the school. It was followed by drafting the letters asking for the help of the identified stakeholders. Those that were in the local community, were just given in person. As to those who were in far places and outside of the country, emails were sent while some were sent through Facebook messenger.

The researcher also uploaded several videos asking for help through the school's Facebook page which were then shared by the teachers on their own various social media accounts and social groups.

Post Implementation

After the researcher implemented the strategy, the researcher proceeded to implement the appropriate recovery response. Afterward, the Brigada Eskwela reports for the school years 2020-2021 and 2021-2022 were gathered. A document review was then conducted to analyze the data. The participants of the study were expected to understand the value of tapping into their social capital as a means to help the school improve its financial management system in the areas of fund generation, crisis response, and speedy recovery.

Qualitative data from the online survey questionnaire given to randomly selected teachers and parents were also collated and analyzed. The data were carefully examined, coded, and analyzed. Results were then derived from the data analysis. Observations made during the implementation of the strategies served as the basis for reflection.

Chapter 2

ACTION RESEARCH METHODS

The skillful management of financial resources to fulfill school obligations and needs is very crucial, especially in times of crisis. The ability of schools to mobilize needed resources speeds up recovery after a crisis and greatly impacts the delivery of quality education. Thus, schools must be able to come up with proactive strategies to raise funds from stakeholders to fill in the fiscal gaps and resolve their needs timely. Based on these premises, the researcher crafted a plan of action to study the effectiveness of the implemented financial management strategies to improve the school's crisis response and speed up its recovery.

Design

This study utilized the explanatory sequential research design. There were two phases in this study. Initially, the researcher collected and analyzed the quantitative data generated over a span of a year. This was taken from the document review based on the school Brigada Eskwela reports. Secondly, qualitative data were subsequently collected in the second phase of the study and were related to the outcomes from the first phase. Themes and sub-themes were developed based on the answers of the participants in the open-ended focus questions in the survey.

Participants and other Sources of Data and Information

The participants of this study were thirty-two (32) randomly selected teachers and parents of Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts for the school year 2021-2022. The participants were given an online survey questionnaire.

For the documents review, Brigada Eskwela Reports for the school years 2020-2021 and school year 2021-2022 were used mainly as quantitative data and information sources.

Data Gathering Procedures

Aside from the document review using the Brigada Eskwela Reports for the school years 2020-2021 and 2021-2022, the researcher also utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire to gather data as to the participant's perception of the effectiveness of the employed strategy to improve the school's financial resources generated and if there was an improvement in the school's financial management to crisis response and recovery.

Data Analysis

Absolute difference was used to get the real number difference between the funds generated before and after the strategy was implemented.

Formula:

$$| (\text{funds generated after the strategy}) - (\text{funds generated before the strategy}) | = |X|$$

Where X is the absolute difference.

The relative difference was then used to determine if there was an improvement in the school's financial resources generated after the strategy was implemented in terms of percentage.

Formula:

$$\frac{(\text{funds generated before the strategy}) - (\text{funds generated after the strategy})}{(\text{funds generated before the strategy})} \times 100 = |\text{RD}|$$

Where RD is the relative difference expressed in its absolute value and percent.

Qualitative data from the online survey questionnaire given to randomly selected teachers and parents were also collated and analyzed. The data were carefully examined, coded, and analyzed to determine the effectiveness of the strategy.

The researcher employed ethnographic and thematic data analysis to analyze the qualitative data. Similarly, the data gathered from the survey questionnaire was turned into pie charts and thematic analysis was used to capture themes and patterns to answer the research questions and identify actions to take to further improve the innovation. Results were then derived from the data analysis. Observations made during the implementation of the strategies served as the basis for reflection.

Ethical Considerations

Consent. The participants in this study were informed that their participation was optional. They were told that if they feel that doing so may be against their interest, they were free to not participate. Additionally, they were also made aware that the study was only done for academic purposes and that the information collected from them would only be utilized for those objectives.

Confidentiality Pledge. The information collected in this study was kept secret and will not be made public. Codes were used to substitute the participants' names. All throughout, the files containing the study data were safeguarded and encrypted. To keep the data secure, files containing study data must be safeguarded and encrypted.

Authorization to Access Private Information. As mandated by the Data Privacy Act of 2012, (RA 10173), the interests of the participants were carefully safeguarded. The researcher made sure that any relevant data or information about the study's participants was not accessed, transferred, or copied without the permission and authorization of the Regional Research Committee.

Chapter 3

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND REFLECTION

This chapter discussed the results of analyzing the data gathered and presented the interpretation of the data collected. Reflections were then drawn out from personal insights and observations made during the entire course of the study. Recommendations were then proposed to further improve the study as well as the strategy being implemented.

Results

Table 1

Generated School Funds Before & After the Strategy Implementation, 2020-2022

Brigada Eskwela Funds Generated (in Pesos)	
Before the Strategy Was Implemented (SY 2020-2021)	After the Strategy Was Implemented (SY 2021-2022)
170, 220.00	3, 217, 578.00
Absolute Difference	3, 047, 358.00
Relative Difference (Percentage Increase)	1790.25 %

Note: Generated school funds were taken from BE reports of PCPGTVSFA 2020-2022

Table 1 shows the Brigada Eskwela Funds of the school as generated before and after the strategy was implemented. From the table, the absolute difference of 3, 047, 358.00 can be gleaned. From the same table above, a relative difference of 1790.25 percent

increase in funds generated can be seen. This implied that when compared to its previously generated value, the strategy implemented by the researcher clearly and significantly improved the school's latest financial resources generated after the strategy was implemented.

These results corroborated the findings of Bilkisu (2018) wherein the skillful management of financial resources contributes greatly to the success of any school plan, which in turn, improves overall school performance. The results also implied that implementing digital transformations in the way we do things, greatly contributes to improving the quality of life in general and education in particular as pointed out by Dung (2021).

1. *Social Mobilization Need: Understanding Level by the Participants*

The succeeding data results were gathered from the survey questionnaire given to the thirty-two randomly selected participants of the study. Figures 1 to 6 showed the participants' level of understanding in terms of the need for social mobilization.

Figure 1

Importance of the strategy to raise funds for the school to timely respond to the recovery needs

In figure 1, 81.3% of the participants highly understood while 13.8% understood the importance of the school's social mobilization and online engagement efforts to raise

funds for the school to timely respond to the recovery needs after the devastation brought by typhoon Odette.

Figure 2

Importance of tapping internal & external stakeholders to bridge fiscal gaps

In figure 2 above, 81.3% of the participants highly understood while 13.8% of them understood the importance of tapping internal and external stakeholders to help bridge the fiscal gaps of the school.

Figure 3

Importance of finding alternative sources of additional school funds

In figure 3, 75% of the participants highly understood the while 25% understood the fact that the school MOOE is not enough to cover all the financial needs of the school thus, there was a need to find alternative sources for additional school funds.

Figure 4

Importance of building and practicing diverse forms of social capital in mobilizing capacities during recovery

In figure 4 above, 62.5% of the participants highly understood while 37.5% understood the importance of building and practicing diverse forms of social capital before a disturbance so that capacities can be mobilized during recovery.

Figure 5

Importance of immediate action for school recovery

In figure 5, 81.3% of the participants highly understood while 18.8% understood the importance of immediate action for school recovery after the onslaught of typhoon Odette.

Figure 6

Importance of ensuring a safe and secure learning environment for the learners

In figure 6, 81.3% of the participants highly understood while 18.8% understood the importance of ensuring a safe and secure learning environment for the learners as they go back to in-person face-to-face classes.

From the same survey, 81.3 % said they highly understood the importance and value of partnership with stakeholders in enabling speedy school recovery while 78.1% of the participants said they understood the importance of building social connections and online engagement to reach out to potential benefactors.

2. Effectiveness Perception

As to the effectiveness of the employed strategy, 81.3% totally agreed on the helpfulness of social mobilization and online engagement in addressing school financial gaps. Moreover, 71.9% said they totally agree that the use of social mobilization and online engagement in tapping social capital did deliver the needed equipment and tools for the school. In addition, 71.9% also said that they recommend to other schools the adoption of the same strategy to aid them in their financial needs. Lastly, 68.8% of the participants totally agreed that the employed strategy was effective and a huge success.

3. Themes and Sub-themes

Table 2

Themes	Sub-themes
Theme 1: Experiences and thoughts on the effectiveness of the strategy in improving the school's fiscal management system in responding to crisis and recovery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provided personal engagement • empowered stakeholder participation • provided additional funds • paved the way for successful face-to-face classes
Theme 2: Significant changes and transformations brought by implementing the strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strengthened partnerships • enhanced collaboration • provided faster recovery • united stakeholders
Theme 3: Identified areas to improve the strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use more social media platforms • widen external linkages • ensure transparency and sustainability

Summary Table of Themes and Sub-themes

From the open-ended questions from the survey questionnaire, three themes emerged. The first theme was focused on the experiences and thoughts on the effectiveness of the strategy in improving the school's fiscal management system in responding to crisis and recovery. The participants found the strategy was effective in its implementation since it did not only provided additional funds for the school, but also provided personal engagement, empowered stakeholder participation, and ultimately paved the way for the successful return to face-to-face classes of the learners.

The second theme centered on the perceived significant changes and transformations that were observed by the participants. The observed changes and transformations were in terms of strengthened partnerships, enhanced collaboration, faster recovery, and more united stakeholders.

Lastly, the third theme focused on the areas of improvement to further enhance the social mobilization strategy. The identified areas for improvement include the use of more social media platforms, widening external linkages, and ensuring transparency and sustainability.

Reflections

Prompt, timely, and fast crisis and recovery responses were made possible by tapping stakeholders through a combination of traditional social mobilization and online engagement. It was evident that people found the strategy of tapping social capital effective as it involved them, enhanced their collaboration, and fostered unity of purpose to a common goal. When people work together, a planned strategy has a greater chance of success. Lastly, a shared vision will likely result in shared accountability, thereby raising the chance for greater effectiveness in coming up with the end goal, as implied in this study.

Recommendations

The following steps are recommended by the researcher:

1. To further improve the study, other researchers may look into other angles and factors that need to be considered in social mobilization.
2. Other researchers may also look into other strategies that may offer sustainability in social mobilization strategies using social capital and online engagement.
3. The results of this study need to be studied by other school administrators for replication as it may also be applicable in their respective school settings and context.

Chapter 4

ACTION RESEARCH WORK PLANS AND TIMELINES

Introductory Statement

The researcher identified the need to raise additional funds on top of the MOOE allocation of the school to speed up recovery efforts after the devastation brought by super

typhoon Odette. The researcher acknowledged that previous social mobilization strategies were not as effective as they were expected.

Rationale

The researcher implemented a new strategy by tapping social capital in its social mobilization and online engagement as a way to improve its financial management response to crisis and recovery.

Objectives

This study sought to determine the effectiveness of tapping social capital in social mobilization and online engagement to improve the school’s financial management system in response to crisis and recovery.

Specifically, the answers to the following questions were sought:

1. Was there an improvement in the school’s financial resources generated after the strategy was implemented?
2. What was the level of understanding of the participants as to the importance of the implemented strategy in improving the school’s financial management system in terms of crisis response and speed of recovery after the strategy was implemented?
3. Was the strategy effective according to the perception of the teachers and parents?
4. How can the strategy be further improved?

Table 1. Implementation Scheme

Activities	Target days	Person Involved	Resources Needed	Expected Outcome
Pre- Implementation 1. Writing and submission of research proposal 2. Created and oriented the social	7 days	Researcher	Bond papers Inks Folders Fasteners	The research proposal was crafted and submitted. The social mobilization team was created and

mobilization team to help implement the strategy 3. Asked for consent from the participants of the study				oriented as to their roles. Participants were informed about the study.
Implementation 1. The strategy was implemented.	60 days	Researchers Participants Co-teachers	Bond papers Inks Folders Fasteners	The financial management system in terms of funds raised was improved, speeding up crisis response and recovery.
Post Implementation 1. Document review and an online survey were conducted. 2. Data analysis and interpretation were conducted. 3. Dissemination of the results was done thru LAC, Research Conference, and others.	5 days	Researchers Participants	Bond papers Inks Folders Fasteners	The effectiveness of the given strategy was determined.

Action Research Dissemination

The researcher disseminated the results of this action research through the Division Research Conference participated by PSDS's, and school heads of the different districts of the Division of Bohol. The research was also shared through the State of the School Address (SOSA) in the researcher's school as well as in the Learning Action Cells (LC) Sessions conducted in the same school.

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Appendix A

Transmittal Letter

November 13, 2021

RAINELDA B. GALULA, PH.D.
Public Schools District Supervisor
Bien Unido District
Bien Unido, Bohol

Ma'am:

The undersigned respectfully endorse to your office this action research study entitled: *“Social Mobilization And Online Engagement: Tapping Social Capital To Improve The School's Financial Management System In Crisis Response And Recovery”* in Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts.

In view thereof, I request your office for consent to conduct the said research on the selected participants of Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts for the school year 2021-2022. With your kind approval, I will make the necessary arrangements with the concerned research participants.

Attached are the research questions and the research tools to be used for your reference.

I guarantee that the information gathered shall be kept confidential and be used for academic purposes only. I am anticipating your favorable response to this request.

Thank you and God Bless!

Truly yours,

MICHAEL G. HORMACHUELOS, PH.D.
Researcher

DR. BIANITO A. DAGATAN, CESO V
Schools Division Superintendent
Bohol Division
City of Tagbilaran

Sir:

The undersigned respectfully endorse to the School Division Superintendent, Division of Bohol the action research study entitled: “*Social Mobilization And Online Engagement: Tapping Social Capital To Improve The School's Financial Management System In Crisis Response And Recovery*” in Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts.

In view thereof, I request your office for consent to conduct the said research on the selected participants of Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts for the school year 2021-2022. With your kind approval, I will make the necessary arrangements with the concerned research participants.

Attached are the research questions and the research tools to be used for your reference.

I guarantee that the information gathered shall be kept confidential and be used for academic purposes only. I am anticipating your favorable response to this request.

Thank you and God Bless!

Truly yours,

RAINELDA B. GALULA, PH.D.
Public Schools District Supervisor
Bien Unido District

Appendix B. Research Instrument

Social Mobilization And Online Engagement: Tapping Social Capital to Improve School's Fiscal Management System in Crisis Response & Recovery - Online Survey

Prepared By: Michael G. Hormachuelos, Ph.D.

(Note: This online survey form will be used to capture data as to the effectivity of the implementation of Social Mobilization and Online Engagement to Improve Fiscal Management Response in Times of Crisis at Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Tech. Voc. School of Fisheries and Arts for SY 2021-2022.

Dear participant,

This questionnaire intends to determine your perception as to the effectiveness of the implementation of the Social Mobilization and Online Engagement to Improve Fiscal Management Response In Times of Crisis at Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Tech. Voc. School of Fisheries and Arts for SY 2021-2022. Thus, it may serve as an objective basis for continuous improvement and future research. Given this, please give an honest assessment of the strategy. Kindly check the column that best reflects your answer/perception. Thank you for your generous cooperation.

I. UNDERSTANDING LEVEL OF THE NEED FOR SOCIAL MOBILIZATION

Direction: Read each statement carefully and assess your understanding based on the scale below:

Response	Interpretation
Highly Understood	Social Mobilization is highly needed
Adequately Understood	Social Mobilization is adequately needed
Slightly Understood	Social Mobilization is slightly needed
Not Understood	Social Mobilization is not needed

1. Understood the importance of the school's social mobilization and online engagement efforts to raise funds for the school to timely respond to the recovery needs after the devastation brought by typhoon Odette.

- Not Understood
- Slightly Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

2. Understood the importance of tapping internal and external stakeholders to help bridge the fiscal gaps of the school.

- Not Understood
- Slightly Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

3. Understood the fact that the school MOOE is not enough to cover all the financial needs of the school thus, there is a need to find alternative sources for additional school funds.

- Not Understood
- Slightly Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

4. Understood the importance of building and practicing diverse forms of social capital before a disturbance so that capacities can be mobilized during recovery.

- Not Understood
- Slightly Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

5. Understood the importance of immediate action for school recovery after the onslaught of typhoon Odette.

- Not Understood
- Slightly Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

6. Understood the importance of ensuring a safe and secure learning environment for the learners as they go back to in-person face-to-face classes.

- Not Understood
- Slightly Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

7. Understood the importance and value of partnership with stakeholders in enabling speedy school recovery from the damages of typhoon Odette.

- Not Understood
- Slightly Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

8. Understood the importance of building social connections and online engagement as a way for the school to reach out to potential benefactors.

- Not Understood
- Slightly Understood
- Understood
- Highly Understood

B. OVERALL EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SOCIAL MOBILIZATION AND ONLINE ENGAGEMENT: TAPPING SOCIAL CAPITAL TO IMPROVE THE SCHOOL'S FISCAL RESPONSE AFTER TYPHOON ODETTE

Kindly give your overall evaluation of the Social Mobilization and Online Engagement strategy of the school by selecting the appropriate statement of choice.

Direction: Read each statement carefully and assess your understanding based on the scale below:

Response	Interpretation
Totally Agree	Social Mobilization is highly effective
Agree	Social Mobilization is adequately effective
Slightly Agree	Social Mobilization is slightly effective
Disagree	Social Mobilization is not effective

1. The social mobilization and online engagement were really helpful in addressing the financial gaps of the school.

- Totally Agree
- Agree
- Slightly Agree
- Disagree

2. The social mobilization and online engagement were able to deliver the needed resources in repairing the damaged classrooms, especially the roofs.

- Totally Agree
- Agree
- Slightly Agree
- Disagree

3. The social mobilization and online engagement were able to deliver the needed tools and equipment for the learners and teachers.

- Totally Agree
- Agree
- Slightly Agree
- Disagree

4. Continuing the social mobilization and online engagement strategy of the school to raise additional funds is something that I will recommend to continue.

- Totally Agree
- Agree
- Slightly Agree
- Disagree

5. Continuing the social mobilization and online engagement strategy of the school to raise additional funds is something that I will recommend to other schools.

- Totally Agree
- Agree
- Slightly Agree
- Disagree

6. As I see it, the social mobilization and online engagement strategy of the school to raise additional funds was effective and a huge success.

- Totally Agree
- Agree
- Slightly Agree
- Disagree

C. FOCUS QUESTIONS

Direction: This part intends to explore and describe your significant experiences, thoughts, and feelings in terms of the effectiveness of the social mobilization and online engagement efforts of the school to improve its fiscal response after the crisis brought on by typhoon Odette. Your comments and narratives will serve as an objective basis for future improvements in the strategy.

In view of this, please give your honest responses to the questions. Thank you for your generous cooperation.

1. How would you describe your experiences and thoughts about the effectiveness and usefulness of the social mobilization and online engagement efforts of the school in improving its fiscal response after the crisis brought on by typhoon Odette?

2. What do you think were the significant changes or transformations that were brought about by the social mobilization and online engagement efforts of the school?

3. What can you suggest to improve the implementation of the social mobilization and online engagement efforts of the school in improving its fiscal responses in times of crisis?

Appendix C. Research Proposal Application Form and Endorsement of Immediate Supervisor/s

A. RESEARCH INFORMATION

RESEARCH TITLE	
SOCIAL MOBILIZATION AND ONLINE ENGAGEMENT: TAPPING SOCIAL CAPITAL TO IMPROVE THE SCHOOL'S FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN CRISIS RESPONSE AND RECOVERY	
SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH	
This study sought to determine the effectiveness of tapping social capital in social mobilization and online engagement to improve the school's financial management system in response to crisis and recovery.	
RESEARCH AGENDA CATEGORY	
<p>(Please check <u>only one</u>) Main Themes</p> <p>1. Teaching and Learning <input type="checkbox"/> a. Instruction <input type="checkbox"/> b. Curriculum <input type="checkbox"/> c. Learners <input type="checkbox"/> d. Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> e. Learning Outcomes</p> <p>2. Child Protection <input type="checkbox"/> a. Bullying <input type="checkbox"/> b. Teenage Pregnancy <input type="checkbox"/> c. Child Abuse <input type="checkbox"/> d. Addiction <input type="checkbox"/> e. Media Consumption</p> <p>3. Human Resource Development <input type="checkbox"/> a. Teaching and Non-Teaching Qualifications and Hiring <input type="checkbox"/> b. Career Development <input type="checkbox"/> c. Employee Welfare</p> <p>4. Governance <input type="checkbox"/> a. Planning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> b. Finance <input type="checkbox"/> c. Program Management <input type="checkbox"/> d. Transparency and Accountability <input type="checkbox"/> e. Evaluation</p>	<p>(Please check any, if applicable) Cut-Across Themes</p> <p>1. Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) <input type="checkbox"/> a. Prevention and Mitigation <input type="checkbox"/> b. Preparedness <input type="checkbox"/> c. Response <input type="checkbox"/> d. Rehabilitation and Recovery</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Gender and Development (GAD)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Inclusive Education</p>
	<p>RESEARCH SCOPE <i>(please check <u>only one</u>)</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> Region <input type="checkbox"/> Division <input type="checkbox"/> District <input type="checkbox"/> School</p>
	<p>RESEARCH CATEGORY <i>(please check <u>only one</u>)</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Action Research <input type="checkbox"/> Basic Research</p>
FUND SOURCE (e.g. BERF, SEF, others)*	AMOUNT
MOOE	10,020.00
TOTAL AMOUNT	10,020.00

**indicate also if proponent will use personal funds*

B. PROPONENT INFORMATION

B.1. LEAD PROPONENT / INDIVIDUAL PROPONENT

LAST NAME: HORMACHUELOS		FIRST NAME: MICHAEL		MIDDLE NAME: GRANADA	
BIRTHDATE (MM/DD/YYYY) 01/09/1979		SEX: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female		POSITION: (e.g. Teacher 1, Master Teacher 1...) Secondary School Principal 1	
CONTACT NUMBER 1: 09499465791		CONTACT NUMBER 2: 09163627834		EMAIL ADDRESS: hormachuelosmichael001@deped.gov.ph	
NAME OF SCHOOL / DISTRICT / OFFICE ASSIGNED Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Tech-Voc Sch. Of Fisheries & Arts				CONTACT NUMBER OF SCHOOL / DISTRICT / OFFICE 09163627834	
ADDRESS OF SCHOOL / DISTRICT / OFFICE ASSIGNED Puerto San Pedro, Bien Unido, Bohol				DIVISION BOHOL	REGION VII
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT (DEGREE TITLE) <i>enumerate from bachelor's degree up to doctorate degree</i>		TITLE OF THESIS / RELATED RESEARCH PROJECT <i>for the last three (3) years</i>			
Bachelor in Secondary Education major in English					
Masters in Physics					
Masters in Educational Management - CAR					
Doctor of Philosophy					
SIGNATURE OF PROPONENT: 					

IMMEDIATE SUPERVISOR'S CONFORME

I hereby endorse the attached research proposal. I certify that the proponent has the capacity to conduct a research study without compromising his official functions.

	<i>Lead Proponent's Immediate Supervisor</i>	<i>2nd Proponent's Immediate Supervisor</i>	<i>3rd Proponent's Immediate Supervisor</i>
Full Name	Rainelda B. Galula, Ph.D.		
Position / Designation	Public Schools District Supervisor		
School / District / Office	District of Bien Unido		
Date	April 25, 2022		
Signature			

Appendix D. Declaration of Anti-Plagiarism

Republic of the Philippines
 Department of Education
DIVISION OF BOHOL
 Region VII, Central Visayas
 City of Tagbilaran

DECLARATION OF ANTI-PLAGIARISM

1. I, Michael G. Hormachuelos, understand that plagiarism is the act of taking and using another’s ideas and works and passing them off as one’s own. This includes explicitly copying the whole work of another person and/or using some parts of such work without proper acknowledgment and referencing thereof.
2. I understand that violation of this declaration and commitment shall be subject to consequences and shall be dealt with accordingly by the Department of Education, as stipulated in DO. No. 16, s 2017 entitled “Research Management Guidelines (RMG).”
3. I hereby attest to the originality of this research proposal and have cited properly all the references used. I further commit that all deliverables and the final research study emanating from this proposal shall be of original content. I shall use appropriate citations in referencing other works from various sources.

	<i>Lead Proponent</i>	<i>2nd Proponent</i>	<i>3rd Proponent</i>
Full Name	Hormachuelos, Michael G.		
Position / Designation	Secondary School Principal 1		
School / District / Office	Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Tech Voc Sch of Fisheries & Arts		
Date	April 25, 2022		
Signature			

Appendix E. Declaration of Absence of Conflict of Interest

Republic of the Philippines
 Department of Education
DIVISION OF BOHOL
 Region VII, Central Visayas
 City of Tagbilaran

DECLARATION OF ABSENCE OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST

1. I, **Michael G. Hormachuelos**, understand that conflict of interest refers to situations in which financial or other personal considerations may compromise my judgment in evaluating, conducting, or reporting research.
2. I hereby declare that I do not have any personal conflict of interest that may arise from my/our application and submission of my research proposal. I understand that my/our research proposal may be returned to me/us if found out that there is a conflict of interest during the initial screening as per item A(ii), Section V(B) of the Research Management Guidelines.
4. Further, in case of any form of conflict of interest (possible or actual) which may inadvertently emerge during the conduct of my research. I will duly report it to the research committee for immediate action.
5. I understand that I may be held accountable by the Department of Education for any conflict of interest which I have intentionally concealed.

	<i>Lead Proponent</i>	<i>2nd Proponent</i>	<i>3rd Proponent</i>
Full Name	Hormachuelos, Michael G.		
Position / Designation	Secondary School Principal 1		
School / District / Office	Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Tech Voc Sch of Fisheries & Arts		
Date	April 25, 2022		
Signature			

Appendix F. Curriculum Vitae

I. PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name: **Michael G. Hormachuelos**
Address: Poblacion, Bien Unido, Bohol
Birthday: January 9, 1979
Age: 43
Gender: Male
Status: Married
Contact No. : 09479465791
Email: hormachuelosmichael001@deped.gov.ph

II. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Elementary:	Dagohoy Central Elementary School Dagohoy, Bohol 1995-1996 Valedictorian
Secondary:	Dagohoy National High School Dagohoy, Bohol 1995-1996 Valedictorian
College:	University of San Carlos Cebu City 1999-2000 DOST Scholar
Graduate Studies:	De La Salle University City of Manila 2005-2006 DepEd - NEAP Scholar
	Selinus University Milan, Italy 2018-2019
	Bohol Island State University Tagbilaran City Ongoing

III. EMPLOYMENT HISTORY

Date started teaching: June 17, 2002
Years of Experience: 20 years
Current Position: Secondary School Principal 1
Current Station: Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Tech. Voc. Sch. Of Fisheries
& Arts

Annex G. Certification of Action Research Implementation

This is to certify that **Michael G. Hormachuelos** of **Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Tech. Voc. Sch. Of Fisheries & Arts**, District of Bien Unido have conducted an Action Research entitled, **“SOCIAL MOBILIZATION AND ONLINE ENGAGEMENT: TAPPING SOCIAL CAPITAL TO IMPROVE THE SCHOOL'S FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN CRISIS RESPONSE AND RECOVERY”** and implemented their output of the study in that particular school mentioned above, in the Division of Bohol.

This is to certify further that the output which is **“SOCIAL MOBILIZATION AND ONLINE ENGAGEMENT: TAPPING SOCIAL CAPITAL TO IMPROVE THE SCHOOL'S FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN CRISIS RESPONSE AND RECOVERY”**, has greatly improved the school’s financial management system in terms of its crisis and recovery response. The result benefited the school by adequately funding the needed repairs after super typhoon Odette as well as replacing several damaged instructional equipment and tools.

This certification is given on the 15th day of November 2022 at Bien Unido, Bohol, Philippines.

RAINELDA B. GALULA, PH.D.
OIC - Public Schools District Supervisor
District of Bien Unido

Annex H. Utilization & Dissemination Report

The output of the action research entitled **“SOCIAL MOBILIZATION AND ONLINE ENGAGEMENT: TAPPING SOCIAL CAPITAL TO IMPROVE THE SCHOOL'S FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN CRISIS RESPONSE AND RECOVERY”**, was properly utilized and has greatly improved the school’s financial management system in terms of its crisis and recovery response. The result benefited the school by adequately funding the needed repairs after super typhoon Odette as well as replacing several damaged instructional equipment and tools. The funds raised by the implemented strategy enabled Pres. Carlos P. Garcia Technical Vocational School of Fisheries and Arts to do the necessary preparations in time for the opening of the face-to-face classes for the school year 2022-2022.

Moreover, the researcher was also able to present the findings division-level conference participated by PSDSs and school heads as he was asked to share it as one of the best practices in the school. The study’s findings were also disseminated through the State Of the School Address (SOSA), District Conference of Schol Heads during DsMEA, and LAC sessions in the school.

MICHAEL G. HORMACHUELOS, PH.D.
Researcher

ANNEX I. Certification of Similarity Index

SOCIAL MOBILIZATION AND ONLINE ENGAGEMENT TAPPING SOCIAL CAPITAL TO IMPROVE THE SCHOOL'S FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN CRISIS RESPONSE AND RECOVERY

ORIGINALITY REPORT

8% SIMILARITY INDEX	3% INTERNET SOURCES	3% PUBLICATIONS	6% STUDENT PAPERS
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PRIMARY SOURCES

1	Submitted to Bohol Island State University - Candijay Campus Student Paper	2%
2	Submitted to Campbellsville University Student Paper	2%
3	Lucie K. Ozanne, Julie L. Ozanne. "Disaster Recovery: How Ad Hoc Marketing Systems Build and Mobilize Social Capital for Service Delivery", Journal of Public Policy & Marketing, 2021 Publication	1%
4	Submitted to Divine Word Univresity Student Paper	1%
5	www.researchgate.net Internet Source	1%
6	digitalcommons.fiu.edu Internet Source	1%
7	Submitted to uv	

Student Paper

1%

Exclude quotes On
Exclude bibliography On

Exclude matches Off

ANNEX J. Financial Report

SUMMARY OF EXPENSES

<i>Activities</i>	<i>Item Description/ Particular</i>	<i>Quantity</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Unit Cost</i>	<i>Total Amount</i>
Writing and submission of the research proposal	Supplies and material -Reproduction and printing cost -folders	6	-copies of papers	85.00	510.00
Submission of Research proposal to the Division Office for approval	Travel expenses and food allowance	1	person	1,000.00	1,000.00
Preparation of research instruments modules permits and other requisites	Supplies and material -bond paper	1	Reams	250.00	250.00
	-ink	2	bottles	340.00	680.00
	-folders	10	pieces	8.00	80.00
Attend meetings and conferences on the progress of research	Travel expenses Food allowance Accommodation	1	person	6,000.00	6,000.00
Reproduction of Soft Bound research copies	Reproduction, printing costs	10	copies	150.00	1,500.00
TOTAL					10,020.00

Annex 5A. Minimum Requirements of Completed Action Research Report

DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION
DIVISION OF BOHOL
 REGION VII, CENTRAL VII

City of Tagbilaran

Minimum Requirements of Completed Action Research Report

5-A Checklist for COMPLETED ACTION RESEARCH REPORT			
Section	Yes	No	Remarks
Title Page	✓		
Abstract	✓		
Acknowledgment	✓		
Table of Contents			
Chapter 1 INTRODUCTION <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Context and Rationale • Action Research Questions • Innovation/Intervention/Strategy 	✓		
Chapter 2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants and/or other Sources of Data and Information • Data Gathering Methods • Ethical Considerations • Data Analysis 	✓		
Chapter 3 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND REFLECTION <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results • Reflection • Recommendation 	✓		
Chapter 4 IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	✓		
References	✓		
Appendices <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transmittal • Research Instrument • Application Form & Endorsement • Declaration of Anti-plagiarism • Declaration of Absence of Conflict of Interest • Research Proponent's Profile • Certification of Implementation from SH/PSDS • Certification of Anti-plagiarism Review • Financial Report • Pictorial (Optional) • Other Relevant Research Documents 	✓		

Checked by _____ Date Checked _____ NOTED:

 Secretariat, SDRC

AMELIA CORTIDOR, PH.D.
 SEPS, Research Coordinator

PICTORIALS

Pictures were taken during the research dissemination done by the researcher during the SDO Bohol Research Management Conference held at Metro Center Hotel, Tagbilaran City on November 10, 2022.

